

Community Participation for Sustainable Development Tourism in Bang Noi Floating Market, Bangkoti District, Samut Songkhram Province

Bua Srikos, Phusit Phukamchanoad, Suwaree Yordchim

Abstract—The purpose is to study the model and characteristic of participation of the suitable community to lead to develop permanent water marketing in Bang Noi Floating Market, Bangkoti District, Samut Songkhram Province. A total of 342 survey questionnaire was administered to potential respondents. The researchers interviewed the leader of the community. Appreciation Influence Control (AIC) was used to talk with 20 villagers on arena. The findings revealed that overall, most people had the middle level of the participation in developing the durable Bang Noi Floating Market, Bangkoti, Samut Songkhram Province and in aspects of gaining benefits from developing it with atmosphere and a beautiful view for tourism. For example, the landscape is beautiful with public utilities. The participation in preserving and developing Bang Noi Floating Market remains in the former way of life. The basic factor of person affects to the participation of people such as age, level of education, career, and income per month. Most participants are the original hosts that have houses and shops located in the marketing and neighbor. These people involve with the benefits and have the power to make a water marketing strategy, the major role to set the information database. It also found that the leader and the villagers play the important role in setting a five-physical database. Data include level of information such as position of village, territory of village, road, river, and premises. Information of culture consists of a two-level of information, interesting point, and Itinerary. The information occurs from presenting and practicing by the leader and villagers in the community. All of phases are presented for listening and investigating database together in both the leader and villagers in the process of participation.

Keywords—Community Participation, Sustainable Development, Encouragement Tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

ONE of the most beautiful floating markets that the most foreigners enjoy visiting is The Bang Noi Floating Market. In the past, it used to be an outstanding part to trade with China. It was around with Junks from abroad and people from other nations as it was located on Maeklong-Tha Jeen River, The main river of Samut Songkhram Province. King Rama 2 used to visit in 1909 as he loved to call in people who lived around there and traded with foreigners himself. Generally, The Bang Noi Floating Market is a huge land of fruit and more than 80 percent of people are farmers and agriculturists Such as coconuts, rose apple, lynes, pomelos,

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and bananas. Someone owns business such as trading, owner small industrial factories like wood factories, docks, coffin shop, fresh market, public routine markets, and private market in front of Koa Khaew Temple and open space of Samorn Paiboon Company. Also there are home shops, commercial buildings, and two banks: Bangkok Bank and Saving Bank along Amphawa-Bangnok Kwak Highway. From details above, this shows that a government aims to the importance of this area and always develops by starting from basic infrastructures first and also encouraging mass transportation public health according to policies and missions. What's more, the government takes more roles and realizes on the development of education and tourism which are basis of community economy of Kra Dang Nga Sub District. The populating of floating markets in Thailand increases rapidly in each part of the country; thus, Mr. Somphob Rattanepaibol, The Chairman of Kra Dang Nga Municipality continually develops the land in order to increase the number of tourists in Samut Songkhram Province each year. Antithetically, not only does the number of tourist increase but also many investors own the lands to run their own business. This affects to less participation from the local and lack of database of community that supports to then development of The Bang Noi Floating Market [1]. Concerning problems and factors affected to this floating market, a researcher believes that in the next few years all areas will be occupied by investors from outside and this will lessen the qualities of lives of surely fade local tradition and culture that connects to agriculture of the community. Everything's changing will be good or bad support to living and occupation of people in community. It's hard to expect in future. No one can predict what will happen so long as the local people have less power to own and take care of their lands. It is left with questions: How can the local in this community participate in developing this floating market and how can this floating market become sustainable one to this province? And the result of this research will be a great mechanism to integrate a developing plan to The Bang Noi Floating Market based on a theory of tourism management of The Bang Noi Community.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study the model and characteristic of participation of the suitable community leading to develop sustainable floating market in The Bang Noi Floating Market, Bangkokthi District, Samut Songkhram Province.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

There are 2,341 persons who dwell in Kadaeng-Nga Municipality. A researcher provides 342 sampling to collect information that can cover 4 communities [2]. Then data will be analyzed in order to find out levels of participation based on descriptive statistics with arithmetic mean) and standard deviation to describe general information of group. For instance, the level of average of 5 namely 4.21-5.00 (maximum) 3.41-4.20 (high) 2.61-3.40 (medium) 2.60-1.81 (low) 1.0-1.80 (minimum).

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

From the research, people dwell in Kadang-Nga Municipality; Samudsongkham Province showed 2.59 as an average level of participation to develop sustainable floating market in The Bang Noi Floating Market. In view of various sides, the researcher found that people with the average level took the first tour sides while the last two sides were people with the low level respectively:

- Sharing Benefits (average 2.79)
- Following up and Evaluation (average 2.73)
- Acknowledging (average 2.70)
- Considering and Determining (average 2.61)
- Proceeding (average 2.38)
- Brainstorming and sharing (average 2.32)

This indicated that people there got benefits from the floating market by following up and evaluating based on understanding determining and brainstorming with people in a group of community as can be seen in the Table I.

TABLE I
 LEVEL OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN THE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND THE OVERALL

Participation for Sustainable Development Tourism	Mean	S.D.	Level
Acknowledging	2.70	0.95	Medium
Sharing suggestion	2.32	1.03	Low
Sharing are considering developing towards development	2.61	0.99	Medium
Follow up Institutions and evaluations	2.73	1.06	Medium
Sharing benefit	2.79	0.92	Medium
Total	2.59	0.85	Medium

The interesting aspect of the second part is a minimum level for complicity. The comments are as follows:

The participation of community towards sustainable tourism of The Bang Noi Floating Market Bang Khon Tee District Samut Songkhram Province can be classified by overall proceeding with the low level of an average 2.38 when considering from a table. Next the participation of people to proceed in was in the medium level found only 1 from the maximum to minimum. Those were (1) The participation for public relation of The Bang Noi Floating Market and with an average 2.77 and the low level were (2) The participation to encourage The Bang Noi Floating Market Project with an average of 2.39 (3) The participation of planning for the Bang Noi Floating Market Project with an average of 2.37 (4) The

participation of to be committee of the Bang Noi Floating Market Development Project with an average of 2.18 (5) The participation of budget to developing tourism in the Bang Noi Floating Market. This showed that people, who lived in this area, realized and wanted to promote their floating market which is useful to the tourist development as can be seen in Table II.

TABLE II
 LEVEL OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN THE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT BY PARTICIPATION IN COMMUNICATION AND SUGGESTION

Participation in Communication and Suggestion	Mean	S.D.	Level
planning for tourist attention development	2.37	1.13	Low
Sharing are considering developing project held by official government	2.45	1.13	Low
Sharing suggestion towards development	2.38	1.11	Low
Participation to development	2.20	1.11	Low
Sharing suggestion towards development	2.19	1.11	Low
Total	2.32	1.03	Low

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TABLE III
 LEVEL OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN THE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND THE OVERALL

Participation	Mean	S.D.	Level
The Sharing of benefit	2.18	1.19	Low
Participants about plans to develop the market and Involved in promoting	2.37	1.21	Low
Participation to development The Bang Noi Floating market	2.39	1.17	Low
Co-funding for tourism development	2.18	1.17	Low
Participation in publicity tour	2.77	1.25	Medium
Total	2.38	1.05	Low

4 group's people from different communities take role to produce tourist maps which benefit to both people and community

Fig. 1 Researcher and people participatory meeting

Fig. 2 Community Leader and Committee take opinion in meeting

Fig. 3 Observation of Research Team

V.CONCLUSION

Most people overall indicate a medium level of participation in sustainable develop of the Bang Noi Floating Market. The Most important thing that people participate in is cooperation with the development for The Bang Noi Floating Market project and agreement to consider each project held by government. Also they realize voting to be abolished for The Bang Noi Floating Market Development and cooperate with public relation including following up developing project in terms of scenery and atmosphere. However, people must take

more roles to join activities in order to find ways to earn budget for preceding each project. The researcher come with the conclusion that the way to develop sustainable tourism for The Bang Noi floating Market is to sustain environment and local atmosphere together with patronizing a market at KohYai Temple to be like KohKhaew Temple. This is what local people really desire.

Fig. 4 Researcher and people working

Fig. 5 Participate Commenting for Community Area Map

Fig. 6 Community Leader and Researcher take conclusion meeting

VI. DISCUSSION

Most people overall indicate a medium level of participation in sustainable development of The Bang Noi Floating Market. A side with a medium level is sharing benefits, following up and evaluating, determining and knowledge sharing. This shows that those people who get benefits from this floating market will support to develop. However, people must have more chance to suggest and proceed because people dare to share and suggest only if there are some outside organization take roles. This participates to slow development and lead only to a medium level e.g. the research of readiness of people toward community development of NongKhem, Bangkok to be a culture attraction [3]. The result shows more readily of people in a medium level as they are confident to selection committee. So community committee are the most powerful people to shift the future of community [4] which shows that a community with great cooperation from people and committee leads to peace and prosperity to a community. The most essential factor is that committee definitely must join activities or projects directly with people including money support for public relation as this is the way to support a community sustainable development and people know how to apply the philosophy of sufficiency economy as a waterfront living lifestyle [5].

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